

An optically oscillating ephemeral intermediate in uncatalyzed bromate driven oscillators

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An optically oscillating ephemeral intermediate was found in the uncatalyzed bromate driven oscillator, phenol-BrO₃⁻-H₂SO₄ or aniline-BrO₃⁻-H₂SO₄ system in a batch reactor. These oscillations were found to be in phase with the redox potential oscillations. The oscillating ephemeral intermediate in phenol system was found to be phenoxy radical; however, in case of aniline system anilino free radical was found. An oxidation-reduction step was suggested for redox potential oscillations in these systems.

The chemical oscillators reported till date are mostly oxidation-reduction systems. The fact that some organic substrates shows oscillations with bromate alone^{1,2} incited us to investigate the species responsible for oxidation-reduction reaction in the aromatics, particularly in phenol and aniline systems which are representatives of these classes of oscillators. Noyes *et al.* have proposed a modified version of FKN mechanism for polyhydric phenol³ which shows oscillations with acidic bromate alone. They have postulated semiquinone radical as an intermediate species which is formed by oxidation of polyhydric phenols :

where polyhydric alcohol acts as a reduced metal ion catalyst. Herbine and Field⁴ have modified OKN^{5,6} mechanism. The metal ion oxidation reaction of classical B-Z reaction system has been replaced by

where phenol acts as a reduced metal ion catalyst. They have also recognized that the source of formation of PhO[•] is the oxidation of phenol by BrO₂[•] and Br⁻ and consumption of free radical occurs in two ways i.e. by dimerization or further oxidation leading to semiquinone radical. These two paths are dependent upon the stability of radical². However dimerization path does not seem to be significant because Orban and Körös⁶ have analyzed the reaction products as 1,2-benzoquinone, 1,4-benzoquinone, hydroquinone, and its bromoderivatives. However, Tokestine and Handlirova⁷ have found 2,6-dibromo-1,4 benzoquinone, 2-bromo-1,4 benzoquinone, 1,4-benzoquinone, 4-bromo-1,2-benzoquinone, 1,2-dihydroxy benzene and hydroquinone

as products, which indicates that further oxidation of phenoxy radical is facilitated rather than dimerization leading to the formation of semiquinone radical and finally quinone and its bromoderivatives as stable products. We have measured absorption spectra of oscillating reaction mixture of phenol-BrO₃⁻-H₂SO₄ and aniline - BrO₃⁻-H₂SO₄ systems and oscillation in absorbance which seem to be contributing to the mechanism of uncatalyzed oscillators.

Experimental

Phenol, aniline, hydroquinone, NaBrO₃ and H₂SO₄ of analytical grade were used as such without further purification. The solutions were prepared in dilute sulfuric acid. The temperature of the system was maintained at 25° and the solution was continuously stirred by a magnetic stirrer. The potential was monitored with a Pt electrode coupled with a reference calomel electrode connected to the reaction mixture by a KNO₃ salt bridge. The oscillation in absorbance was monitored by a spectrophotometer. In order to see the phase relationship in some of the experiments redox potential and absorbance oscillations were measured simultaneously. For measurement of oscillation in absorbance 10 mm path length and 2.5 ml reaction mixture volume was taken. The absorbance spectrum of oscillatory reaction mixture was measured by a quartz cell having optical path length 0.02 cm. The oscillation in absorbance for shorter wave length band was measured in 1.25 ml reaction mixture volume and 5 mm optical path length.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectrum of phenol in 1.0 M H₂SO₄ is shown in Fig. 1. The absorbance band of phenol at 210 nm

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of phenol- BrO_3^- - H_2SO_4 taken in 2 mm path length quartz cell : (i) acidic solution 0.002 M phenol in 1 M H_2SO_4 , (ii) phenol (0.002 M) + BrO_3^- (0.025 M) + H_2SO_4 (1.0 M) oscillatory reaction mixture : (a) after 2 min, (b) after 13 min, (c) after 24 min.

and 270 nm disappeared immediately after the addition of BrO_3^- to the aqueous acidic solution of phenol, and new bands appeared at 244 nm, 290 nm and 392 nm. Out of these absorption bands the absorption intensity of 392 nm band increased during induction period and then decreased in oscillatory manner and finally disappeared. These oscillations in absorbance are found to be in phase with the redox potential oscillations. The absorbance intensity of 392 nm band disappeared finally.

The absorption spectrum of aqueous acidic solution of aniline has absorption band at 252 nm as shown in Fig. 2. The intensity of 252 nm band increased on the addition of BrO_3^- and a new rather broad band due to an intermediate appeared at 310 nm. The intensity of this band increased in an oscillatory manner and then decreased. These absorbance oscillations were found to be in phase with redox potential oscillations. The intensity of 310 nm absorption band finally disappeared.

Chopin-Dumas⁸ have shown that unstable radical prefers dimerization rather than further oxidation; however independent experimental analysis by Orban and Körös⁶ as well as Tokestine and Handlirova⁷ indicates that no dimer-

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of aniline system : (a) aqueous solution (0.0018 M), optical path length 2 mm, temp. 25°, (b) oscillatory reaction mixture, [aniline] = 0.0018 M, $[\text{BrO}_3^-]$ = 0.025 M, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = 2.0 M, temp. = 25°, optical path length = 2 mm.

ized product was formed. Therefore, oxidation route seems to be favour as for disappearance of phenoxy radical rather than dimerization. Therefore, it appears logical to assume that semiquinone radical may be a possible intermediate in the process of formation of quinone as product. Our absorption spectrum measurement of phenol system shows one broad band at 392 nm and an other at 290 nm. The band position of 392 nm band is coincident with that of phenoxy radical measured by Raghwan and Field⁹ as well as by Porter¹⁰; however, band shape is different. Their absorption band has two absorption peaks at 385 nm and 402 nm but we have found only one broad band. This may be due to semiquinone radical which is heaped up to the phenoxy radical band. The possibility of Br₂ absorption maximum at 395 nm may be ignored as similar experiments with aniline do not show any band at 395 nm, which is in agreement with Körös *et al.* observations¹¹. Therefore it appears that semiquinone radical is contributing to absorption band around 400 nm. A similar experimental with hydroquinone as an organic substrate does not seem to be suitable as semiquinone is a quite stable radical. Hydroquinone-BrO₃⁻-H₂SO₄ system shows only one potentiometric oscillation. On addition of 0.053 M solution acidic BrO₃⁻ into the 0.082 M solution of hydroquinone in 3.0 M H₂SO₄ orange yellow colour appears which instantaneously changes to light orange yellow colour. Then the yellow colour disappears very slowly followed by one oscillation. UV-Visible absorption spectra measurement shows one broad band at 412 nm, which is matching with that obtained by Land and Porter¹² by flash photolysis in paraffin viscous medium. The band was characterized as due to semiquinone radical. This is in agreement with the observation of Körös *et al.*¹ and Dumas *et al.*² that the stable radical does not favour the oscillations. Therefore it appears that phenoxy radical is one of the important radicals which favour the oscillations and is rapidly converted to semiquinone radical which causes the damping of oscillations. If we assume that the intermediate is phenoxy radical then oxidation reaction of phenol may be written as

Further we know that the metal catalyst Ce⁴⁺ can be reduced by Br⁻ as

A similar reaction may be written for the reduction of phenoxy radical by Br⁻

It appears that PhO[•]/PhOH redox couple is oscillating in this system and absorption of PhO is oscillating in phase with redox potential oscillations.

In aniline system eq. (1) may be replaced by

and eq. (3) may be replaced by

where, the redox pair PhNH₂/PhNH[•] oscillates in phase with absorpoion oscillations in aniline system.

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